

Shannon's Entropy Following from Scaling for Quantum Particle in a Box?

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Shannon's entropy – Sum over i $P(i) \ln(P(i))$, where $P(i)$ is the probability for event i , has the form of an average of the function $\ln(P(i))$ which is sometimes given the name information in the literature. This entropy form, however, also follows for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas by taking \ln of the number of permutations of a distributed variable, namely energy, i.e. $\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i P(e_i))$.

In this note, we consider the case of a single quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls. Such a problem is solved using wavefunctions (both spatial and momentum), i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $W(x)$ is the spatial wavefunction and $a(p)$, the momentum. Given that a one dimensional box has a length L , the idea of scaling appears, in particular in the behaviour of $W(x)$ and $a(p)$. Given that p and x are conjugate variables, it is not surprising that one is associated with \sqrt{L} and the other with $1/\sqrt{L}$. At the wavefunction level one does not have distributed variables or classical probabilities as in the Shannon's entropy situation, but one can create them using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$. We try to explain why one cannot know both distributed variables at the same time in the scenario. We also consider the situation of changing L to L_1 such that the form of $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ do not change. If one wishes to have a measure in terms of distributed probabilities $P(x)$, $P(p)$, which remains unchanged in such a situation, one may see that this may be accomplished by using $\ln(P(p))$ or $\ln(P(x))$. Taking an average of this quantity seems to be a natural thing to do and this leads to a sum of Shannon's entropies for $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ such that this sum does not depend on L . In other words, adiabatic quantum motion does not change this measure, but scaling behaviour of the wavefunctions $W(x)$, $a(p)$ is the underlying key, we argue.

Distributed Variables in Quantum Mechanics

Classically a particle with a constant p, v has a probability:

$$P(x,p)dx = dx/L \quad ((1))$$

$P(x,p)$ is positive, real and normalized and is associated with a distributed variable x . The problem is that this probability gives no information about p which imparts impulses. As a result, one cannot use such a probability when describing an interaction with say a two slit apparatus in a probabilistic manner. One requires a dynamic probability because one deals with a single particle.

We have suggested in (1), that ((1)) is really a static probability because it contains no p value. Thus, one may postulate a $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ such that:

$$P(p,x) = P_{\text{special}}(-p,x)P_{\text{special}}(p,x) \quad ((2))$$

This leads to the complex valued $P_{\text{special}}(p,x) = c \exp(ipx)$ ((3))

((3)) allows one to use p and x values at the same time, whereas ((1)) doesn't. Any p value has a probability of dx/L at the distributed variable level.

We argue that this is interesting because if one creates:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) contains various physical p values, but in the distributed world, these exist independently with the probability dx/L . In other words, given a specific p value, each x point has the same probability or one does not know what x is. On the other hand, applying the freezing out of motion recipe ((2))

to $W(x)$ yields:

$$W^*(x)W(x) = P(x) \quad ((5))$$

In this case, one has a distribution in x , but knows nothing about p . Thus, the quantum approach leads separately to classical probability distributions in x and p , i.e. ((5)) and $a^*(p)a(p)$, but one deals either with x or with p , but not the two together at the distributed level. At the wavefunction level, however, one has p and x values together.

A main point we wish to make is that particles interact and so one needs a probability which describes such interactions, namely $\exp(ipx)$. Even for what seems like a distribution problem, i.e. a bound state problem, $\exp(ipx)$ describes interactions (impulse hits) with the average function $V(x)$, i.e. the potential. As a result, one uses a wavefunction when computing average kinetic energy in a conservation of energy equation, i.e.

$$\left(\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right) / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((6))$$

For a one dimensional box of length L with infinite potential walls and the center at $x=0$ (2):

$$W(x) = \sqrt{2/L} \sin(kn x) \text{ for } n \text{ even and } \sqrt{2/L} \cos(kn x) \text{ for } n \text{ odd where } kn = n \pi/L \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{and } a(p) = 1/\sqrt{2\pi\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} W_n(x) \exp(-ikx) dx \quad ((8))$$

Wavefunctions and Scaling

If one examines ((7)) and ((8)) one may immediately see that the length L is involved in scaling. In fact, ((7)) is a function in x/L with a factor of $\sqrt{1/L}$. The freezing out form is $W(x)W(x)$ so one again has a function of x/L , but now the factor is $1/L$. If one integrates over dx , then one multiplies by L so that dx becomes dx/L . As a result, L disappears. The issue is that if one takes an average using $P(x)$ with a function of $W(x)W(x)$, then the factor of $1/L$ is still present in this function and this needs to be kept in mind.

Examining ((8)) one sees that $W_n(x)$ has a factor of $1/\sqrt{L}$ and otherwise is a function of x/L . Thus, kx becomes $kL x/L$ and dx becomes $L dx/L$. Thus, $a(p)$ has a factor of \sqrt{L} and is a function of kL . If one integrates $a^*(k)a(k)$ over k , then $P(k)$ contains the factor L and the function is in the form $P(kL)$ so dk becomes Ldk/L . Thus, once again there is no L dependence. If one, however, takes an average over some function of $P(k)$, the L factor is still present.

Functional Average Which Removes L Dependence

In the world of the wavefunction, which is used to solve the problem of a particle in an infinite well, one deals with scaling. Probabilities here are not real and positive. In the distributed world with $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$, however, they are. One may ask the question: Is there a function whose average in the distributed world eliminates L ?

One sees that $P(x)$ carries the factor $1/L$ while $P(p)$ carries the factor of L . If one has a sum of these two distributed variables which cannot be known at the same time for reasons described above, one may note that one needs a function of the form:

$$F(L) + F(1/L) = 0 \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{A solution of ((9)) is } F = \ln \quad ((9))$$

Thus, $\ln(P(x))$ and $\ln(P(p))$ carry the L information as well as other information and allow for L to disappear.

What are the physical consequences of such a result? The quantity:

$$-\int dx P(x) \ln(P(x)) - \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p)) \quad ((10))$$

is independent of L . In other words, if one increases L , the length of the potential well slowly in time such that the wavefunctions $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ don't change their form, (i.e. the adiabatic approximation in quantum mechanics), then ((10)) does not depend on L , but only on the form of the wavefunction. In other words, scaling of wavefunctions of conjugate variables p and x at the wavefunction level leads to factors of $1/L$ and L as one may see loosely from px becoming $pL x/L$. P and x are conjugate variables in the quantum wavefunction picture, i.e. in $\exp(ipx)$ and not in $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$. The emergence of two distributed variables p and x with $P(p)$ and $P(x)$, not at the wavelength level and independent in the sense that one cannot x and p together, also follows from the wavefunction picture as do the scaling factors. The wavefunctions are clearly different for L and $L1$, but at the level of a distributed variable, there is an average function ((10)) for which the L dependence of the x distribution cancels the L dependence of the momentum distribution. In classical physics, it seems one would only have L dependence associated with space.

If one wishes to consider this in terms of the first law of thermodynamics and takes ((10)) as entropy, then E clearly changes with L , but this seems to be assigned strictly to work as the general form of the wavefunction does not change. Thus, the form of the wavefunction remaining the same seems to be equivalent to no heat being added.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Shannon's entropy usually applies to real positive probabilities associated with a distributed variable. For the classical probability $P(p,x)dx=dx/L$, there is no p or v , so we argue it is static. This then cannot be used to describe impulse hits in space using probability, i.e. a steady stream picture. We suggest that there exists a $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ which must contain p explicitly and that freezing out motion yields: $P(x,p)= P_{\text{special}}(x,-p)P_{\text{special}}(x,p)$ leading to $\exp(ipx)$. This probability exists in a nondistributed world with x and p being known. For a given p , the distributed x probability is $P(x,p)$, so there is no information about a specific x . If one creates $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and uses it to create an average kinetic energy which may be added to $V(x)$ to yield a constant E , then one may find both $W(x)$ and $a(p)$, with the frozen probabilities (classical probabilities, i.e. nondynamic, non collisional probabilities) being $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$.

We consider the problem of a particle in a box and examine scaling issues, where L is the length of the box. In the quantum wavefunction scenario $\exp(ipx)$, p and x are conjugate variables. Thus, if x scales as x/L , p scales as Lp for $\exp(ipx)$ to remain unchanged. One finds that $W(x)$ is a function of x/L with a factor of $1/\sqrt{L}$ and $a(p)$ a function of Lp with a factor of \sqrt{L} . If one uses distributed variables, i.e. $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, then one has the factors $1/L$ and L which are on the same footing as x/L and pL . In fact, the integrals $\int dx P(x) = \int dp P(p)=1$ and so cannot depend on L . If one uses $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ to create an average of some function of $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ then one must consider the factors $1/L$ and L . We ask: Is there a function such that L disappears if one adds the $P(x)$ average to the $P(p)$ one? We show that $\ln(P(x))$ is such a function.

We apply this to the situation of a quantum adiabatic change in the length of the box L such that the wavefunction forms do not change. For the wavefunctions, there is a change in energy and scaling, but at the distributed level ($P(x)$ and $P(p)$), the form has not changed and one may argue that work has been done, but no heat added, so to speak. In such a sense, $-\int dx P(x)\ln(P(x)) - \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$ may represent entropy, although the absence of L follows directly from scaling and the conjugate behaviour of p and x in $\exp(ipx)$. In such a sense, adding a photon to $W_n(x)$ so that it becomes $W_{n+1}(x)$ would suggest that heat has been added. In general, a noninfinite potential would also involve a change in the classical turning points suggesting work being done.

References

1. [Particle in a box - Wikipedia](#)